

Relationships among Data used as Migration Indicators

**Charles D. Coleman
Melissa L. Therrien**

**Population Estimates Branch
Population Division
U.S. Census Bureau
Washington, DC 20233-8800**

June 4, 2001

This paper reports the results of research and analysis undertaken by Census Bureau staff. It has undergone a more limited review than official Census Bureau publications. This report is released to inform interested parties of research and to encourage discussion. The views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Census Bureau.

1. Introduction

The Population Estimates Branch (PEB), Population Division, of the U.S. Census Bureau uses four indicators of migration to generate intercensal county population estimates.¹ We analyze indicators of household migration and group quarters (GQ) population changes for the two age groups aged under 65 (“young”) and 65 and older (“old.”) This paper uses correlation and regression analyses to determine the relationships between these migration indicators for 1990-99. Our first goal is to determine whether any of the migration indicators can predict others. If so, then the set of migration indicators can be reduced. If not, this negative result validates PEB’s current estimation methodology. The correlations are run on both the whole data set and on subsamples obtained by stratifying on various variables.

Our second goal is to determine the causal structure of the data. That is, we find out the predictive relationships between the variables. This provides a depth of understanding of the data that is unobtainable otherwise. Section 2 explains the sources and applications of the migration indicators. Section 3 describes the data and methods used in this paper. Section 4 describes the analyses and their results. Subsection 4.1 and 4.2 cover the correlation and causality analyses, respectively. Section 5 discusses the implications of the results. Section 6 concludes by summarizing the data, methods, and results.

¹ The “counties” also include county equivalents such as independent incorporated cities and Alaskan Census Areas. For simplicity, these will be subsumed into counties in the text.

2. Source and Application of Migration Indicators

The Census Bureau's intercensal estimates program uses three sources of domestic migration data. The Census Bureau collects, processes and analyzes data supplied by the Internal Revenue Service (IRS), the Health Care Financing Administration (HCFA), and the Federal-State Cooperative for Population Estimates (FSCPE). Each data set is used to derive migration for different segments of the population, as described in Subsections 2.1-2.3 below.

2.1 Internal Revenue Service Data

Each year, the Census Bureau receives a file containing an extract of information derived from IRS personal income tax returns of the previous year. This file contains, for each return, information such as social security numbers, names, number of dependents, filing status, income, and addresses (including zip code). The returns in the current year are matched by the filer's social security number to those in the file from the previous year. If a taxpayer files a return in different zip codes in two successive years, he is considered a potential migrant. If the zip codes are in different counties, then the taxpayer and any dependents are considered migrants from the first county to the second.² This assumes that the filer and his dependents migrate together. Net migrants are calculated as immigrants, persons migrating into a county, less outmigrants, persons migrating out of a county. The net "young" household migration rate of a county is estimated to be the number of net migrants divided by the sum of the numbers of

² The data are also examined for anomalies which can cause spurious migrations. The most frequent cause is conversion from rural to urban delivery, which changes zip codes and can cause nonmigrants to appear as migrants.

nonmigrants (persons who do not move between counties) and outmigrants. For each county and each period, year n to year $n + 1$, net “young” household migration is the product of the “young” household population in year n and the net “young” household migration rate for that period. Research is underway to determine the effects of deriving migrations of filers and dependents separately, thereby increasing the accuracy of IRS-derived migration data. (Pearson and Sater, 1999) Under U.S.C. Title 13, the data supplied by the IRS are highly confidential and cannot be disseminated outside of the Census Bureau.

2.2 Health Care Financing Administration Data

The Census Bureau obtains an annual file containing data on the number of enrollees in Medicare, for each state and county. The Census Bureau uses these total Medicare enrollment figures by county to estimate a migration rate for the “old” population. Because some Medicare data include only the state of residence, which the Census Bureau cannot use to determine migration rates for county-level estimates, these data are allocated to the counties within the state. The “old” migration rate is computed as the change in adjusted enrollment between two successive years divided by the “old” population in the first year. The calculation of net “old” migration is similar to that of net “young” migration. The Census Bureau assumes that this coverage rate stays constant throughout the decade, given that no additional information exists to estimate changes in the coverage rate. Additionally, Medicare enrollment is adjusted each year to account for underenrollment of the “old” population. This is done by developing a coverage rate

calculated as the ratio of Medicare enrollees in 1990 to the “old” population enumerated in the 1990 census.

2.3 Federal-State Cooperative for Population Estimates Data

GQ data are collected annually from FSCPE members. Each year, PEB sends a comprehensive listing of GQ facilities, including prisons, nursing homes, and prisons, to the FSCPE members. Each member, ideally, verifies the existence of the facilities, and supplies population data for each facility. The Census Bureau does not actually use GQ change in estimating the population, but, rather, uses the changes in populations of actual GQ facilities. This is necessary because of the inconsistency between the GQ data supplied by the FSCPE members and those enumerated in the decennial census. Because GQ populations are not household populations, household migration rates are not applied to these populations. Rather, we use GQ change as a measure to indicate migration among GQ populations. The Census Bureau computes GQ change separately for the “young” and “old” populations.

3. Data and Methods

We used a combination of correlation analysis, scatterplots and regressions to determine the relationships between and causal structure of the migration variables, including both the levels and rates of migration indicators. The analyses were performed separately for the “young” population and the “old” population. In addition, the analyses were performed on variables based on the two household migrations together. The universe consisted of all 3,141 counties and county equivalents. Correlations were

performed on the migration variables for the entire data set to understand the overall behavior of the data set. Correlations were performed on partitions of the data set to identify possible divergences from overall trends. Bivariate scatterplots were used to visually examine data, including the identification of outliers. Regressions were used to determine predictability of variables. The final regressions constructed the causal structure of the data.

3.1 Migration Data

Migration of persons in households was obtained from data previously calculated for use in the intercensal population estimates program. Group quarters change was derived by finding the difference between GQ populations in years n and $n + 1$, where n is one of the years 1990-1998. The averages of these variables for the period 1990-1999 were used as the level data. Rate data were constructed by dividing the level data by the July 1, 1990 estimated population and are expressed in per cent.

3.2 Correlation

We used two measures of correlation, the Pearson product-moment coefficient, R , and the Spearman rank-correlation coefficient, ρ . These are measures of the direction and strength of a joint, monotonic relationship between two random variables. A relationship is monotonic, up to random error, if an increase in one variable is associated with either an increase or decrease in the other, but not both. In this paper, we are concerned with testing the correlations between IRS migration, Medicare migration, and GQ change. An important proviso is that correlation does not imply causation.

R measures the amount of spread about the linear least squares regression line, and is calculated by measuring the deviations of the variables from the regression line. It ranges from -1.0, indicating a strong, negative linear correlation, to 1.0, indicating a strong, positive linear correlation. A value of zero indicates no linear relationship. An R with absolute value of .7 or higher is usually considered to be a strong indicator of linear correlation. R is not sensitive to curvilinear relationships. Moreover, R is highly influenced by extreme observations. Significance testing is made using a null hypothesis of bivariate normality. This test is not robust against departures from this null distribution. Appendix A provides the formula for R .

ρ measures the amount of spread about the true, nonlinear regression line. It is calculated by summing the squares of the differences of ranks of the variables. ρ ranges from -1.0, indicating perfect disagreement between the corresponding ranks, to 1.0, indicating perfect agreement between the ranks. $\rho = 0$ indicates no relationship between the ranks. A ρ with absolute value of .7 or higher is usually considered to be a strong indicator of correlation. Appendix A provides the formula for ρ .

The two correlation coefficients can provide information about the linearity or nonlinearity of a relationship. $R > \rho$ generally indicates that the relationship is linear, while $R < \rho$ indicates that the relationship is nonlinear. A scatterplot is generally a good method to assess the form of the relationship. It can also identify outliers which can substantially affect the values of the coefficients.

3.3 Regression

In this paper, we use ordinary least squares regressions to determine the relationships between a dependent and one or more independent variables. These are used in the causality analysis. Linear regression models the dependent variable as the weighted sum of the independent variables. The general form of this model is

$$y_i = b_0 + b_1X_{1i} + b_2X_{2i} + \dots + b_nX_{ni} + e_i$$

where the subscript i indexes the observations, y is the dependent variable, the X_j are the independent variables and the b_j are their coefficients and the e_i are random disturbances, assumed to be independent and identically distributed, with zero expectation and no correlation with the X_j . The larger a b_j , the greater the effect that the corresponding X_j has on y . Each b_j has an associated t -value, which is used to test the hypothesis that $b_j = 0$ against the alternative hypothesis that $b_j \neq 0$. The greater this value, the less likely that the true $b_j = 0$ and the less likely that the observed departure from zero is caused by random variation. The significance level is determined by assuming normally distributed errors and inverting the appropriate Student- t distribution. As the number of observations diverges, the Student- t distribution converges to the standard normal distribution, so that the latter can be used for testing. By convention, a variable is significant when its significance level is less than or equal to 10%. Asymptotically, $|t| > 1.96$ indicates significance.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) measures the amount of variance in the dependent variable “explained” by the regression. It is a goodness-of-fit statistic that provides information about the ability of the regression to predict the dependent variable. R^2 ranges from 0 to 1, from no predictive value to complete predictive value. For

example, the interpretation of $R^2 = 0.65$ is that the model “explains” or “predicts” 65% of the variance in the dependent variable. An R^2 of .5 or higher is usually considered to be a strong indicator of fit.

Subsection 4.2 uses regressions to find the causal structure of the data.

4. Analysis and Findings

The analysis proceeded in two stages. First, an exploratory analysis using correlations identified associations between variables for further exploration. This analysis also provided information about the migration data themselves, shedding insight on PEB’s county estimation processes. The final stage consisted of finding causal structure of the data, using the results of the correlation analysis and prior beliefs about the causality of the variables. Essentially identical causal structures are posited for both the “young” and “old” data. The structures are confirmed by regression analysis, which also rejects alternative explanations.

4.1 Correlation Analysis

We began by calculating correlations of the household migration of each group with household migration for the other group and GQ changes for that group for the total. These correlations were done for both the changes in levels and percentage changes. The percentage changes were calculated by dividing the level changes by the corresponding base populations in 1990. They can be interpreted as propensities to migrate. In addition to correlations for the whole data set, the correlations were computed on data stratified on various variables to determine possible differences in behavior in various subsets of the

universe. The variables included population by age and type (total and GQ) and the corresponding migrations and the percentage changes in these variables. In addition, percentages of population by age for total and GQ population were used. In general, R exceeded ρ , indicating linear relationships. Table 1 displays R for household migration of persons aged less than 65. Table 2 does the same for persons aged 65 or more.

Table 1
Correlation (R) with Migration of Persons aged Less than 65

Variable \ Type	Level	Percentage
GQ change, persons aged less than 65	.11**	.04*
Migration of Person aged 65 or More	.85**	.39**
Total GQ Change	.13**	.05**

Notes:

- * Significant at 5%
- ** Significant at 1%

Table 2
Correlation (R) with Migration of Persons aged 65 or More

Variable \ Type	Level	Percentage
GQ change, persons aged 65 or More	.16**	.01
Migration of Person aged Less than 65	.85**	.39**
Total GQ Change	.11**	.02

Notes:

- * Significant at 5%
- ** Significant at 1%

The most important finding from Tables 1 and 2 is that household migration levels are very highly correlated (.85) and highly significant. The corresponding correlation for the percentages are lower (.39), but still highly significant. Together, these indicate that the

levels of household migration are caused by another variable, which we hypothesize to be population. This hypothesis is confirmed by the fact that $R = .966$ for the two total populations.³ Below, we find evidence that the population level for a particular group predicts its absolute household migration level. The two household migration rates show weaker correlation, but, nonetheless, are highly significant. Thus, the two propensities to migrate are related.

The correlation of migration levels with GQ change levels at first glance would seem to indicate that household and GQ movements are related. However, as Figure 1 shows, a large proportion of the data lie around a constant line migration equals approximately 0. Thus, even though the data are significantly correlated, they are essentially independent: knowledge of migration levels does not produce information about GQ changes. This point will be expanded below. The two main outliers are Los Angeles, CA and Cook, IL, with their large net outmigrations, larger than the populations of most counties. Omitting these would increase R , but not change the explanation.

Stratified correlations of migration with GQ changes are generally stronger and more significant as they pick up a greater proportion of approximately zero household migration levels. Given that migration has no effect on GQ change and that the overall correlation is driven by this line, this result is expected.

³ This is further evidenced by the ability of the population of one group to predict the migration level of the other, albeit less weakly than by the separate regressions of each group's data reported in Subsection 4.2 below. This is, again, caused by the near-perfect correlation of the two populations.

4.2 Causality Analysis

We used regression analysis to determine the causal structure of the data. In essence, we asked the question, “what variables determine what other variables?” We used the interpretation of regression analysis that the independent variables are predictors of the dependent variable. Our criteria included both t -tests and R^2 . Even if a particular independent variable tested significant, if R^2 or that variable’s contribution to R^2 were low, we rejected that independent variable as a predictor of the dependent variable. In these cases, we found that the dependent and rejected independent variables were predicted by another variable, leading to inevitable significance in the regression involving these two variables.

The hypothesized structure is depicted by the directed graph in Figure 2. The graph is identical for both age groups. Each circle, or node, represents a variable. An arrow, or link, between two nodes indicates that the variable from which the arrow points causes the variable to which it points. These relationships are tested by running regressions with the caused and causing variables as the dependent and independent regression variables, respectively. In this context, the independent variable is, statistically, truly a predictor variable. Other relationships suggested by the correlation analysis are similarly tested, but rejected.

In Figure 2, total population causes migration and GQ population. The first relationship arises because, as the population of a county increases, more people can migrate into or out of a county. The second relationship arises from two sources. First, GQ is a component of total population,⁴ so the former must necessarily have some

⁴ Future work will use household population as the primary causal variable. Time did not permit its use in this version.

The predictive power of the 65+ equation is particularly high, as evidenced by its R^2 of .936.

Group Quarters Population → Group Quarters Population Change

The dependent variable, ABSGQCHANGE, is the absolute value of the average group quarters population change, 1990-99.

("young")	$\text{ABSGQCHANGE} = 18.9 + 0.01 \text{ GQPOPULATION}$	$R^2 = .200$
	$\begin{matrix} (10.49) & (28.00) \end{matrix}$	
("old")	$\text{ABSGQCHANGE} = 1.20 + 0.003 \text{ GQPOPULATION}$	$R^2 = .076$
	$\begin{matrix} (3.17) & (214.44) \end{matrix}$	

Although the t -ratios of GQPOPULATION are very significant, the fits for the equations are poor. Since other explanations of GQ change have no substantial explanatory power, we have to accept this link, but with the proviso that it is weak. This has two explanations: missing variables and measurement error. As an example of missing variables, consider the placement of a new prison. The factors influencing its location include land cost, wages, proximity (or lack thereof) to population centers and regulatory environment. We lack data for the first two. The third requires information about the authority undertaking the construction. The last is, for our purposes, unmeasurable. Similar arguments can be made for nursing homes. Higher education dormitories are most influenced by the location of the institution. However, this may result in construction in adjacent counties. Military movements are dictated by both operational military and political concerns. All of these are examples of missing variables.

Measurement error arises as some states and other institutions do not regularly report their GQ populations to PEB. PEB's decision in these cases is to use the latest available GQ population. If any GQ movement occurs, it is missed completely, a type of measurement error.

We added ABSMIGRATION to the above equations to determine if ABSMIGRATION is an important causal factor. Its coefficients were negative and significant. However, the gains in R^2 were negligible, so we rejected it as a causal factor. The negative coefficients are difficult to interpret. They probably reflect the bias caused by the missing variables and measurement errors. Finally, ABSMIGRATION has already been explained by POPULATION, which also indirectly explains ABSGQCHANGE.

Migration → Group Quarters Population Change (Rejected)

This discussion would not be complete without discussing the link Migration → Group Quarters Population Change and why it was rejected. The previous paragraph discussed why the link based on levels was rejected. We also tried to use percent change since 1990 to test this link. The percent changes were obtained by dividing each variable by its 1990 base value. PCGQCHANGE is the average percent change in GQ, 1990-99. PCMIGRATION is the average migration rate, 1990-99, using total population as the base. The equations are

("young")	PCGQCHANGE =	12.0 (4.45)	– 0.01 (0.39)	PCMIGRATION	$R^2 = 0$
("old")	PCGQCHANGE =	0.46 (1.59)	+ 0.203 (1.07)	PCMIGRATION	$R^2 = 0$

Not only is PCMIGRATION insignificant in both cases, but $R^2 = 0$, indicating that these equations have no predictive power and, thus, do not imply causality.

5. Discussion

This paper's most important finding is that the three sources of migration data used by PEB to produce intercensal population county estimates are all useful. Attempts to simplify estimation procedures to use fewer input data sets are futile, as they discard useful information. GQ change has been shown to be essentially independent of the two household migration measures. Therefore, GQ change has to be used to produce estimates. While the two measures of migration (IRS and HCFA) are highly correlated ($R = .85$), they are both useful for estimating the under 65 and 65 and older household populations, respectively. This is evidenced by the lower correlation of their annual percentage changes (.39). This lower correlation reflects differences in the propensities to migrate between the "young" and "old." These different propensities explain the residual lack of fit in the levels. Moreover, the HCFA data set is of high quality.⁵ It would be unwise to discard a data set of this quality. Although the IRS data set is of lower quality, discarding it would lose differences in migration rates between the "young" and "old".

The causal structure of the migration indicators has been determined. Essentially, everything is driven by the population in the two age groups. The total population of one of the age groups strongly predicts both the migration and GQ population in that group.

⁵ Shryock and Siegel (1980), pp. 763-764.

GQ population, similar to total population, predicts GQ changes, although this relationship is weaker due to missing variables and measurement errors. In every case, the larger the predictor variable, the larger the absolute value of the predicted variable can be.

6. Conclusion

This paper has examined the migration data used by PEB to construct county population estimates. Each data series has been shown to contribute useful information to the estimates process. Thus, PEB's county estimation methods, to the extent that they make use of all of these data sets, have been validated. The causal structure of the data has been constructed statistically. The ultimate predictor of the migration variables is population in each age group. Again, this is simply due to the ability of larger counties to sustain larger migrations. Household migration is explained well. GQ changes are poorly explained, due to missing variables and measurement errors.

References

Pearson, Lucinda S. and Douglas K. Sater, "A New Approach to Migration Data Production from Administrative Records: Return-Based vs. People-Based." Presented to the 1999 Southern Demographic Association meetings, San Antonio, October, 1999.

Shryock, Henry S., Jacob S. Siegel and Associates, *The Methods and Materials of Demography*, Fourth printing, revised, Washington: U.S. Government Printing Office, 1980.

Appendix A

Let (X_i, Y_i) be one of a set of n joint observations on the variables X and Y . The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient R is computed as

$$R = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \right)}{\sqrt{\left[n \sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right)^2 \right] \left[n \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \right)^2 \right]}}.$$

The Spearman rank-order correlation coefficient ρ requires more computation.

First, the ranks of the X_i and Y_i are computed. Then, for each pair (X_i, Y_i) , the difference in ranks D_i , are computed. Then,

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n D_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Figure 1

**Average GQ Change against Average Household Migration
“young” Population, All Counties**

Figure 2
Causality Diagram

